

Hot-spots finding with modular gamma-ray system for sort and segregate activities

Gaetano Elio Poma^{1*}, Luigi Cosentino¹, Fabio Longhitano² and Paolo Finocchiaro¹

¹INFN Laboratori Nazionali del Sud, 95123 Catania, Italy

²INFN Sezione di Catania, 95123 Catania, Italy

(*) elio.poma@lns.infn.it

Abstract—In the framework of the PI3SO project (Proximity Imaging System for Sort and Segregate Operations) funded by INFN-Energy project, aimed at the low and intermediate level radioactive waste (radwaste) classification, conditioning and characterization, a scanning system based on a set of 128 gamma-ray detectors based on CsI(Tl) crystal scintillators readout by a silicon photomultiplier have been built and characterized. These are arranged in linear arrays grouped in modules, each one being made of sixteen detection elements compose a sensitive unit, named module, and eight modules define the full-scintillators scanning system. The combination of four modules, arranged in a linear configuration, defines a sliding linear array named detection unit. Placed one above a scanning table and the other parallel to it underneath the table, the two co-moving detection units detect gamma-rays from sparse objects on table improving the detection of partially gamma sources and they will identify the hot-spot. The described modules are suitable for the sorting of nuclear materials and can be used as scanner of radioactive objects placed on a large area surface. Each unit was tested with point-like laboratory gamma-ray ¹³⁷Cs and ²²Na source: the results are promising in view of the integration with the mechanical system which will move the detection units scanning the radwaste. Next step are planned tests in a real environment.

Keywords — radwaste; hot-spot; sort and segregate; SiPM; CsI; gamma-ray scanner.

I. INTRODUCTION

The radioactive materials have to be handled in several fields, for instance radiation waste (radwaste) sorting and segregation [1,2], nuclear medicine [3,4], nuclear physics research and inspections [5,6]. Well defined prescriptions are given concerning material handling, radiation protection and safety. In the framework of radioactive material handling, like in radwaste sorting and segregating operations, the availability of an efficient and easy-to-handle tool to quickly detect gamma radiation hot-spots can be very useful. Furthermore, spectroscopic features, even if with moderate energy resolution, could provide significant benefits. The radwaste

danger decreases with time, therefore the worldwide handling strategy is seal-and-isolate for as long as needed to reduce the activity, and this time can range from a few hours to tens of thousand years.

The IAEA radwaste classification defines 6 classes of radwaste based on overall activity, type and decay time, and a proper storage should be available at all stages in waste processing, for isolation and environmental protection as well as to facilitate retrieval and monitoring [1]. In particular low (LLW) and intermediate (ILW) level waste represent the vast majority of the radwaste worldwide, that are stored into near-surface disposals [1].

As recommended by Innovative UK in conjunction with the Nuclear Decommissioning Authority, the development of innovative solutions i.e. integrated, autonomous toolkits which sort and segregate radwaste generated from nuclear decommissioning activities into optimized containers represents a priority [7]. Each adopted solution requires a tool to monitor the waste radioactivity with the priority in recycling over its disposal, to reduce sorting and segregation process carried out by humans and to increase productivity.

Many tools are commercially available to monitor the radioactivity, in particular gamma-rays which are the most ubiquitous form of radioactivity. Most of the current detection systems are environmental detectors or hand-held detectors. Newly developed compact low-cost radiation detectors, to be directly applied to the radwaste drums, could monitor nuclear materials in place and/or during transportation, detecting possible diversion.

A few projects are currently being developed for the automatic manipulation of nuclear waste, like ROMANS [8] and VIRERO [9] projects, that reduce the waste volume by disassembling and re-sorting radioactive waste material on the basis of the dose-rate levels. Based on system like these, a new compact gamma-ray scanning system named PI3SO (Proximity Imaging System for Sort and Segregate Operations) has been proposed and it is currently under construction.

II. PI3SO PRECURSORS

On the wave of existing projects for sorting and segregation of radwaste, two prototype detectors have been built at INFN-LNS [10] as demonstrators for the quick detection of hot-

spots. The first one is a 60x60 cm² table, named RADSIEVE, featuring an array of scintillating fibers, coupled to Silicon PhotoMultiplier (SiPM) at each end, whose counting rates can tag the presence of hot-spots (fig. 1). RADSIEVE demonstrator has limited performances due to the low detection efficiency of the fibers, poor space resolution, and the ambiguity in position reconstruction in case of more hot-spots.

Fig. 1. RADSIEVE precursor: online gamma-ray counting by moving a ²²Na source (top); detector sketch and photo (bottom).

A second demonstrator, named SCINTABLE, was built as a proof-of-principle in order to overcome the RADSIEVE limitations: it consists of a hundred CsI(Tl) scintillators 1 cm³ with spectroscopic capability, arranged in a 10x10 cm² array and read-out by a 10x10 SiPM array [11].

Fig. 2. SCINTABLE precursor: gamma-ray imaging (left, Monte Carlo simulation) and spectra (right) with ²²Na source (top); detector sketch and photo (bottom).

Based on Monte Carlo simulations and acquired data (fig. 2, top) to characterize the performances of proximity imaging, counting and spectroscopic capabilities [11], SCINTABLE proved the feasibility of the technology and paved the way to the innovative PI3SO system.

PI3SO system has been proposed as SCINTABLE-like detector with the aim of speed up the sorting process of the radwaste material and to reduce operations with human exposure.

The technology explored at INFN-LNS was proved suitable to build a modular gamma detection system as part of a work desk. Realistic configurations are needed as a trade-off between complexity, detection efficiency, counting capability and spectroscopic features.

III. LINEAR GAMMA-RAY ARRAY

Designed as a sensitive table for reclassification of radwaste, PI3SO system is equipped with a reasonable operational 84x128 cm² desk surface: this would imply that to make the whole surface sensitive to the radiation, a thousand of 1 cm³ scintillators are required, which is something too expensive in terms of costs, DAQ and time consuming.

In order to quadratically reduce the complexity of the system and build a near-final device that can be easily employed in real radwaste handling operation, a simplified linear array of scintillators is proposed (fig. 3, 4).

Fig. 3. A PI3SO printed circuit board equipped with 16 SiPMs (top) and 16 CsI(Tl) crystal unit (bottom, white array) compose a module: four modules compose one linear array or detection unit.

Fig. 4. A detection unit with four flanked modules, arranged for DAQ and characterization tests.

Specifically, the tool is composed of two linear arrays named detection units, top and bottom, composed each by 1x64 channels (CsI(Tl)+SiPM) and a work table for the

radwaste support: the bottom array is placed beneath the table and will stay fixed, while the upper one hovering will be moved up and towards the materials placed on the work table, guided by a led-based proximity sensor.

These arrays scan the total table length in 1 cm steps by means of two handling engines which provide also the vertical translation of the linear array in order to avoid possible collisions with the deposited materials. Based on statistical requirements, the acquisition times can be suitably set.

The sensitive element of each detection unit is a CsI(Tl) 1 cm³ crystal [12]. Each crystal is coupled to a 6x6 mm² S14160-6050HS Hamamatsu SiPM by means of optical grease [13], and an array of 16 elements compose a module (fig. 5). The chosen size is a trade-off between detection efficiency, position resolution and compatibility with the SiPM.

The CsI(Tl) has a very good light yield of about 6x10⁴ photons/Me, with a spectral emission centered around the wavelength of 550 nm, and is negligibly hygroscopic. The spectral match between the scintillation light and the SiPM sensitivity gives rise to an overall PDE of about 20%.

Fig. 5. Arrangement of elements for a detection unit made by a CsI(Tl) 1 cm³ crystal [12] and a 6x6 mm² S14160-6050HS SiPM Hamamatsu [13]. A replica of 16 elements makes a detection module, fig. 3.

The CsI(Tl) high density of 4.51 g/cm³ guarantees a good intrinsic detection efficiency. The 1 cm thickness provides a reasonable interaction probability of about 30% (20%) for 600 (1500) keV gamma rays.

SiPMs are biased at low voltage, typically 41.3 V (+2.8 V overbias above breakdown), and the overall 128 output signals are directly connected to two CAEN VX2745 64-channel digitizers operating in charge integration mode [14]. Each channel samples its input waveform at 125 MS/s 16 bits and the data are processed by onboard FPGA, which evaluates the pulse height of the detected signal.

Measurements with gamma sources have been done in order to evaluate its performances in terms of single photon detection capability of SiPM, spectroscopic response, energy resolution, counting rate and peak-to-total spectral efficiency [10].

The measured Full-Width Half-Maximum (FWHM) energy resolution, referred to the 511 and 1275 keV (²²Na) peaks, is 9.7% and 5.8% respectively, in line with typical values reported in literature as well as the 23% peak-to-total efficiency. Due to the decay time of the scintillation light (3

μs), the maximum counting rate permitted in the CsI(Tl) is of the order of 30-50 kHz [10]. This could represent a limitation in case of very high activity because of pile up effects, therefore if necessary future configurations with faster scintillators will be taken into account.

PI3SO feature three different and dependent operational modalities:

- as an overall gamma radiation counter, where the global counting rate is the sum of the individual counting rates;
- as a proximity imaging system (1 cm² pixels);
- as an array of spectroscopic detectors.

In the second and third mode the data from individual channels can be summed, if needed, to improve the statistics at the price of a worse space resolution. The three modes are meant to be used in sequence: first, a coarse and quick counting measurement followed, if a predefined threshold is overcome, by a slower hot-spot search; finally, in case hot spots are found, a finer spectroscopic investigation to look for specific isotopes and/or to perform an energy selective imaging based on full energy gamma detection with reduction of Compton background.

IV. RADWASTE SCANNER

The PI3SO detection units described above, will face each other with an operational table in between, in order to locate the gamma hot-spots, reconstruct their energy spectra and compute the isotope-related images (fig. 6). The need of two detectors arises from the possibility that flat metal objects could be activated on one side only or could shield other objects.

Fig. 6. Sketch of PI3SO scanner: spread radioactive objects, placed on large surface, are scanned by top and bottom linear arrays in XY plane, approaching radwaste during scan along Z direction.

The main application for PI3SO is in the framework of radwaste sorting and repackaging, that involves the opening of drums and sorting their content in order to reduce the volume to be stored. In this application the waste would be placed on top of the work table and the two detector arrays would scan the objects assessing their activity (fig. 6). This would drive the decision on whether an object can be released or should be repacked and stored.

In fig. 6 the configuration of the PI3SO radwaste scanner

based on a fixed table is sketched, with a CCD camera on top and two linear arrays of detectors. The bottom array, almost in contact with the table, is moved in the horizontal direction, synchronized with the upper one. The latter is installed on an up-down actuator in order to be placed as close as possible to the materials to be inspected, according to the indications of a proximity sensor.

The scan is performed in steps of 1 cm and the data are acquired for predefined time intervals. In alternative the acquisition time at each step could be defined depending on the counting rate. In case a hot-spot is detected, the operator can decide to perform a finer spectroscopic analysis.

In fig. 7 a sketch of the radwaste scanner that is going to be developed by a private company is shown. The scanning area is $84 \times 128 \text{ cm}^2$ and the table is made of carbon fiber (1-2 mm thick for a gamma-rays absorption as low as possible). The table is watched by a CCD visible camera, to overlap the visible light image with the gamma-ray image for improving the hot-spot identification. The Anti Collision System (ACS) allows a step by step vertical movement of the upper array, depending on the height of the objects onto the table. It is necessary for reducing as much as possible the distance of the detectors eliminating the collision risks.

A customized software using DAQ digitizers libraries is going to be developed starting from PSD firmware of VX2745 CAEN digitizer [14].

Fig. 7. PI3SO radwaste scanner by SIATEL. 3D view (top-left), carbon fiber plane (bottom-left), side view (right). A CCD camera, top and bottom detectors and the anti-collision system (ACS): it prevents the hitting of top line with the objects placed on the table.

The full development of the detector is carried out at INFN-LNS, including the Monte Carlo simulations in FLUKA [15] required to design a complete model of the system. The SIATEL company [16] has in charge the development of mechanics and controls of the motorized stages, included managing software (fig. 6, 7).

V. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

A test campaign with gamma-ray sources together with FLUKA simulations allowed to study the performances of PI3SO as proximity imaging system. In details, the aim of the

tests is to characterize the detection elements in terms of energy resolution, hot-spot reconstruction and signal-to-noise ratio (S/B ratio) as a function of the channel threshold.

In fig. 8 the scanner implemented in FLUKA framework is shown with the two linear arrays marked in green. In order to speed-up the simulation, a $64 \times 120 \text{ cm}^2$ matrix detector has been implemented as the corresponding of a single linear $64 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ detector (fig. 9). In this way, one simulation by N_{tot} particles represents a complete scan i.e. 120 steps and $N_{\text{tot}} = N_{\text{single}} \times 120$ primary particles simulated.

Simulations consider a single gamma source of 662 keV with activity 10 kBq, 1 cm diameter, isotropically emitted. Source-to-detector distance was varied from 1 to 20 cm, with and without 1 mm carbon fiber in order to evaluate its contribution in terms of gamma-rays absorption and image degradation. Detectors top (det-2) and bottom (det-1) are shown in fig. 9.

Fig. 8. PI3SO radwaste scanner implemented in FLUKA framework: linear array top (det-2) and bottom (det-1) on top (in green); scanner views on bottom.

By varying the source-to-detector distance (1-20 cm), the hot-spot image reconstruction was evaluated in terms of FWHM (fig. 11) showing the role of the source-to-detector distance to localize the hot-spot. As shown in fig. 10, although no collimator has been used, at a distance of 1 cm the system is able to localize and operate a rough imaging of the hot-spot by employing 20 minutes of scanning time i.e. 10 seconds for each step.

This demonstrates that a reduced source-to-detector distance is very important to localize the hot-spot and identify it. The contribution of few mm carbon fiber plane in terms of image degradation and gamma-rays reduction is negligible.

Fig. 9. Sketch on PI3SO scanner implemented in FLUKA framework in bottom (left) and side (center) views, and a zoom of detector with its proprieties (right).

As shown in fig. 11, which report the values of the FWHM of the hot-spot as a function of the source-to-detector distance, hot-spot is well-reconstructed at small distance, worsening at increased distance, which testified the importance to approach objects at each step during scanning.

Fig. 10. Example of hot-spot image reconstruction in proximity imaging, by simulating a 10 kBq 662 keV ^{137}Cs source (1 cm diameter sphere, iso distributed) for 10 sec at each step (1 cm along Y), and a total 20 minute scan. Source-to-detector distance is 1 cm.

Fig. 11. Hot-spot reconstruction as FWHM as function of source-to-

detector distance, by varying the support plane (FC fiber carbon, AIR no plane).

In order to study the system performance in terms of energy calibration and S/B ratio, CsI(Tl)+SiPM characterization has been done in laboratory using two gamma-ray sources using two gamma-ray source: ^{22}Na (662 keV photons) and ^{137}Cs (511, 1275 keV photons), both with 20 kBq activity. S/B ratio represents the quality parameter of a peak and is proportional to the square root of the number of scans.

Fig. 12. Setup for energy calibration's test. A power supply (left) at 41.3 V feed 64 channels at a time of four modules (center), that are connected to digitizer for acquisition.

By using the setup shown in fig. 4, but with the modules arranged in squared configuration, some tests have been done for two set of modules (4 at a time). In particular, the energy calibration has been done for all 128 channels by means of the setup shown in fig. 12, placing both sources at the center of the square. Background spectra have been also acquired to evaluate the detector performance in terms of S/B ratio.

Due to the high number of channels and considering the presence of three peaks in the energy spectrum obtained with from ^{22}Na and ^{137}Cs , an automatic energy calibration procedure for peaks finding and energy reconstruction has been implemented. In fig. 13 an example of the acquired spectrum in channel and energy are show, with the corresponding energy resolutions of the peaks.

Fig. 13. Energy calibration: automatic peaks finding (left), reconstructed calibrated spectrum (right) for one channel.

In particular, the 662 keV peak resolution is 7.3 %, in line with the expectation from existing literature [11].

In order to evaluate detector performance, the energy spectrum quality has been studied for all the channels in terms of S/B ratio as a function of the energy threshold.

Fig. 14. Energy spectrum (left) for source and background runs; S/B ratio as function of channels by varying threshold in [0, 500] channels (right).

In fig. 14 left, the spectra acquired with the source and without the source (background) is reported, considering the S/B ratio from 6 to 22 as function of channel threshold.

Fig. 14 right shows the S/B ratio as a function of the channel threshold, ranging from 6 to 22. By choosing a threshold close to 200, S/B ratio is close to 10 which assures well-resolved small peaks.

Fig. 15 shown the energy resolution of the 662 keV peak for all the SiPMs.

Fig. 15. 662 keV relative energy resolution for all 128 SiPMs: its behavior as a function of # SiPM (left), 1D distribution (right).

The mean value is 6.82 % with sigma 0.71 %. These values evidence that the automatic fitting procedure and crystals response are reliable.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A modular and portable gamma-ray system was described as radwaste scanner for radioactive objects characterization, proximity imaging and selective energy hot-spot findings.

Tests of the PI3SO scanning detectors were done by means of Monte Carlo simulations and experimental tests in order to study its ability to reconstruct hot-spots, proximity images and energy spectra in terms of energy resolution and signal-to-noise ratio.

Due to the large sensitive area and intrinsic detection efficiency of the detectors, as well as reasonable short scanning time for large surface area, the system can be employed in a wide range of radwaste size, shape and radioactive nature, as proved by the obtained preliminary results. The system could also be extended in future with complementary alpha/beta detectors.

PI3SO system can be used in several ways, due to its versatility and modularity, as:

- radwaste sorting and segregation system;
- inspector of large surfaces, floors or walls in decommissioning and/or decontamination of nuclear installations;
- safeguards inspections by IAEA to detect and localize out of control and not declared gamma-emitting materials, as well as unintentional spilling or spread of contaminated materials;
- contamination monitor in nuclear facilities or laboratories;
- supplementary system to the safety baggage scanner in airports.

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